

CHALLENGES AND COPING STRATEGIES OF NURSE MANAGERS ON UNDERSTAFFING IN SELECTED HOSPITALS

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ABSTRACT

The insufficient staffing of nurses in hospitals is a significant concern that can adversely impact patient care, hospital operations, and the welfare of healthcare personnel. This study sought to identify the challenges and coping strategies of nurse managers on understaffing at selected hospitals in Ilagan City, Isabela. This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. The respondents were the 100 nurse managers, specifically nurse supervisors, head nurses, and staff nurses assigned as team leaders of the selected hospitals, identified through total enumeration. The researcher used a self-constructed questionnaire and utilized frequency and percentage distribution, mean, Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis H test, and Spearman's Rho correlation in treating the data. The demographic profile revealed that the majority of the nurse managers are female, aged 36-40, with more than 10 years of service, and hold a bachelor's degree. In addition, nurse managers encountered slight challenges in dealing with understaffing in terms of balancing work distribution, maintaining quality care, addressing staff morale and burnout, recruitment and retention, and managing patient expectations. Moreover, the most commonly employed coping mechanisms by the nurse managers include clear communication, efficient delegation, and the active participation of staff in decision-making processes. The findings also revealed no significant difference in the challenges encountered by the nurse managers and the coping mechanisms employed. Lastly, there was no significant relationship between the two variables.

Keywords: *understaffing, challenges, coping mechanisms, nurse managers*

INTRODUCTION

The insufficient staffing of nurses in hospitals is a significant concern that can adversely impact patient care, hospital operations, and the welfare of healthcare personnel. Insufficient nursing staff to address patient needs may result in diminished patient care, heightened nurse burnout, and elevated turnover rates, among other issues. Addressing nurse understaffing is essential for maintaining high standards of care, supporting the nursing workforce, and ensuring positive patient outcomes.

Nurses are an essential component of healthcare and constitute the largest segment of the health profession. The World Health Statistics Report indicates that there are roughly 29 million nurses and midwives worldwide, with 3.9 million located in the United States. Projections indicate that over one million additional nurses will be required by 2020 (Slattery et al., 2020).

However, nursing understaffing is a major problem in healthcare systems globally, resulting in various negative consequences for both patients and healthcare professionals. When the number of nurses is insufficient to meet patient needs or the demands of the healthcare environment, several challenges can emerge. This may lead to errors, higher morbidity, and mortality rates. In hospitals with high patient-to-nurse ratios, nurses experience burnout, dissatisfaction, and patients experience higher mortality and failure-to-rescue rates than in facilities with lower patient-to-nurse ratios. As stated by Haddad et al. (2024), some states have begun to pass legislation to limit patient-to-nurse ratios.

Due to the persistent understaffing of nurses, nurse managers face a multitude of significant challenges that not only hinder their leadership effectiveness but also disrupt the overall functioning of healthcare units. In the context of the local setting, an initial interview was conducted with nurse managers, who expressed their concerns and frustrations regarding this issue. They emphasized that understaffing places immense pressure on their roles, particularly in key areas such as balancing workload distribution, maintaining the quality of patient care, addressing staff morale and burnout, managing recruitment and retention efforts, and ensuring compliance with regulatory standards. These challenges force nurse managers to constantly juggle competing priorities, often compromising their ability to lead efficiently and ensure optimal outcomes for both staff and patients.

Moreover, while numerous studies have examined the factors contributing to nursing understaffing, there is a noticeable scarcity of research focused on the challenges faced by nurse managers and the coping mechanisms they employ to address this issue. This lack of attention to the managerial perspective highlights a critical gap in the literature, which this study aims to address. By exploring the unique challenges nurse managers encounter and how they navigate the complexities of understaffing, this research sought to contribute valuable insights to improve leadership strategies and healthcare outcomes.

Therefore, the researcher sought to explore the challenges faced by nurse managers and the coping strategies they employ in managing understaffing within a public hospital in Isabela. This study aimed to provide valuable insights that can serve as a foundation for developing targeted interventions and solutions to address the understaffing issue in healthcare settings effectively.

Research Questions

This study sought to identify the challenges and coping strategies of nurse managers on understaffing at selected hospitals in Ilagan City, Isabela.

Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the nurse managers in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Sex;
 - 1.3. Years in Service;
 - 1.4. Highest Educational Attainment;
 - 1.5 Hospital Affiliation?
2. What are the challenges encountered by the nurse managers in dealing with understaffing in terms of:
 - 2.1. Balancing Work Distribution;
 - 2.2. Maintaining Quality Care;
 - 2.3. Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout;
 - 2.4. Recruitment and Retention; and
 - 2.5. Managing Patient Expectations?
3. What are the coping mechanisms employed by nurse managers in addressing understaffing?
4. Is there a significant difference in the challenges encountered by the nurse managers in dealing with understaffing when grouped according to profile variables?
5. Is there a significant difference in the coping mechanisms employed by nurse managers in addressing understaffing when grouped according to profile variables?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered in dealing with understaffing and the coping mechanisms employed by the nurse managers?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to assess and determine the challenges and coping strategies of nurse managers on understaffing at selected hospitals in Ilagan City, Isabela, and the relationship between the two variables. The participants of the study consisted of 100 nurse managers, particularly the nurse supervisors, head nurses, and staff nurses who were assigned as team leaders of the said hospitals chosen through total enumeration. The primary data source was a self-made questionnaire. This consisted of three (3) parts: Part 1 comprised of the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and years in service, highest educational attainment, and hospital affiliation. Part 2 is composed of statements about

the challenges encountered by the nurse managers in understaffing (Loveridge, 2017; Senek et al., 2020). There were 5 dimensions: balancing work distribution with 5 sub-scale items; maintaining quality care with 5 sub-scale items; addressing staff morale and burnout with 5 sub-scale items; recruitment and retention with 5 sub-scale items; and managing patient expectation with 5 sub-scale items. The questionnaire contained response alternatives on a 4-point scale ranging from 4 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree). Part 3 consisted of statements on the coping mechanisms employed by nurse managers in addressing understaffing (Udod et al., 2021; Middleton et al., 2021). There were 10 sub-scale items. The statements were rated using a 5-point scale: 5-always, 4-often, 3-sometimes, 2-rarely, 1-never. The questionnaire was subjected to Cronbach's alpha scoring. The alpha scores of 0.93 (challenges) and 0.86 (strategies) indicated that the instrument was a good and excellent tool, respectively. Approval was obtained from the hospital administrators prior to data collection. To ensure a 100% retrieval rate, the researcher personally collected the completed questionnaires. The collected data were organized, tallied, and subjected to statistical analysis, including frequency and percentage distribution, mean, Kruskal-Wallis H-test, and Mann-Whitney U test.

RESULTS

Part 1. Profile of the Nurse Managers

Table 1: Distribution of the Nurse Managers According to their Demographic Profile

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-25 years old	2	2.0
26-30 years old	3	3.0
31-35 years old	27	27.0
36-40 years old	30	30.0
41-45 years old	13	13.0
46 years old and above	25	25.0
Total	100	100
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	25	25.0
Female	75	75.0
Total	100	100
Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
5 years and below	5	5.0
6-10 years	32	32.0
Above 10 years	63	63.0
Total	100	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Baccalaureate Degree	50	50.0
Master's Degree	49	49.0
Doctorate Degree	1	1.0
Total	100	100

Hospital Affiliation	Frequency	Percentage
Hospital A	40	40.0
Hospital B	35	35.0
Hospital C	25	25.0
Total	100	100

The demographic profile of the nurse managers indicates a varied age distribution, with the predominant group being aged 36–40 years, comprising 30% of the total respondents. Individuals aged 31–35 years constitute 27%, while those aged 46 years and older represent 25%. The data indicate that a considerable number of the nursing workforce are in their mid to late career stages, suggesting a seasoned workforce with extensive expertise. Conversely, merely 5% of nurses are under 30 years of age, suggesting a potential scarcity of new entrants into the profession or a probable retention challenge among younger nurses.

In addition, the nurse managers predominantly consist of females, accounting for 75% of the total, whereas males represent just 25%. This corresponds with global and national trends in the nursing profession, which is characteristically female-dominated. The presence of 25% male nurses indicates an increasing inclusivity and gender diversity within the nursing profession. This sex distribution may affect team dynamics, leadership representation, and patient care strategies in healthcare environments.

Regarding work experience, 63% of the nurse managers have served for over 10 years, while 32% have worked for 6 to 10 years. Merely 5% possess five years of service or less, suggesting that the nursing team predominantly consists of experienced experts. This duration of service indicates a strong commitment to the profession and possibly elevated levels of clinical proficiency.

In terms of educational attainment, 50% of the respondents possess a baccalaureate degree, while approximately the same proportion (49%) have engaged in advanced studies, obtaining a master's degree. Only one participant has obtained a doctorate. This indicates a significant focus on advanced education within the nursing workforce, potentially enhancing evidence-based practice, leadership capabilities, and the quality of patient care.

Lastly, the nurses are evenly allocated across three hospitals, with Hospital A comprising the highest percentage of respondents (40%), followed by Hospital B (35%) and Hospital C (25%). This equitable allocation facilitates comparative assessments among institutions.

Part 2. Challenges Encountered by Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing

2.1. Balancing Work Distribution

Table 2: Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing in terms of Balancing Work Distribution

	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	Distribution of tasks evenly among the remaining staff, leading to workload imbalances.	2.45	Slightly a Challenge
2	Patient care quality and safety are compromised due to limited human resources.	2.44	Slightly a Challenge
3	Inability to balance workloads effectively during understaffing	2.46	Slightly a Challenge
4	Unequal task assignments and perceived favoritism	2.16	Slightly a Challenge
5	Fulfilling supervisory and administrative duties while taking on direct patient care responsibilities to fill staffing gaps.	2.27	Slightly a Challenge
Category Mean		2.36	Slightly a Challenge

Table 2 presents the challenges encountered by the nurse managers in dealing with understaffing, specifically in terms of balancing work distribution. As indicated in the table, the foremost obstacle identified was the difficulty in efficiently balancing duties during understaffed periods (M=2.46), indicating that nurse supervisors recognize the nature of equitably sharing responsibilities without overburdening the team. In addition, a significant issue is the disproportionate allocation of responsibilities among the remaining personnel (M=2.45). This indicates that although it may not be a significant challenge, it nonetheless results in workload disparities that can progressively affect employee morale and performance.

The belief that the quality and safety of patient care may be undermined by insufficient human resources (M= 2.44) underscores a persistent apprehension that understaffing could endanger care outcomes, even if not immediately acknowledged as a significant risk. Challenges, including disproportionate task allocations and perceptions of favoritism, albeit scored marginally lower (M = 2.16), indicate possible concerns with team cohesion and trust. If neglected, these impressions may result in interpersonal disputes, diminished motivation, or unhappiness within the nursing staff.

In like manner, the difficulty of executing supervisory and administrative responsibilities while also engaging in direct patient care (M=2.27) reflects the dual burden many nurse managers carry in times of staff shortages. This circumstance not only impairs their capacity for strategic leadership but may also result in burnout.

The data regarding the obstacles faced by nurse managers in addressing understaffing, particularly in work distribution, suggest that these issues are regarded as only "slightly a challenge" generally, with a category mean of 2.36. This indicates that although the difficulties may not seem significant at first, they are sufficiently present and persistent enough to cause concern. The rating indicates that nurse managers encounter

moderate yet persistent challenges in properly managing staff workloads during periods of constrained human resources. Although not attaining a moderate or severe degree, the existence of these challenges yet indicates significant operational issues. The slight nature of the issues may indicate managers' coping strategies or adaptation, although it also highlights underlying inefficiencies or constraints within staffing systems.

2.2. Maintaining Quality Care

Table 3: Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing in terms of Maintaining Quality Care

	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	Risk of errors, delayed treatments, and overlooked patient needs.	2.26	Slightly a Challenge
2	Risk of having patients who receive impersonalized and incomprehensive care.	2.10	Slightly a Challenge
3	Higher incidence of adverse events such as falls, medication errors, and hospital-acquired infections	2.03	Slightly a Challenge
4	Longer wait times, reduced patient interaction, and diminished care quality	2.21	Slightly a Challenge
5	Monitoring and evaluating patient care outcomes ineffectively	2.09	Slightly a Challenge
Category Mean		2.14	Slightly a Challenge

Table 3 illustrates the challenges encountered by the nurse managers in dealing with understaffing, specifically in terms of maintaining quality care. The most prominent concern relates to the risk of errors, treatment delays, and overlooked patient needs (M=2.26). This suggests that while nurse managers may be managing to uphold basic standards, the pressure of limited staff leaves little room for proactive care and attention to detail. Another important concern is the risk of delivering impersonalized and incomplete care (M=2.10). This indicates that understaffing may lead to a transactional model of care, where staff are focused on completing tasks rather than building patient relationships or providing holistic care.

The data also reflect concerns about an increased likelihood of adverse events such as patient falls, medication errors, and hospital-acquired infection (M=2.03). This relatively lower score may suggest that these risks are being actively mitigated through protocols, yet the fact that it remains a recognized challenge is significant. It emphasizes the delicate balance nurse managers must maintain between managing immediate staffing limitations and ensuring patient safety.

Lastly, the challenges of reduced patient interaction, longer wait times (M=2.21), and ineffective monitoring of patient care outcomes (M=2.09) further indicate the potential degradation in care quality. These issues, though not seen as severe, hint at the

cumulative effect of understaffing on operational efficiency and clinical excellence. Even "slight" challenges, when persistent, can hinder the continuity of care and lead to a gradual decline in healthcare standards.

The data presented on the challenges encountered by nurse managers in dealing with understaffing, particularly in maintaining quality care, reveal that the overall perception of these difficulties is rated as "slightly a challenge," with a category mean of 2.14. The findings point to the presence of subtle but meaningful disruptions in care delivery. Even though the challenges do not reach a moderate or severe level, they signify that nurse managers are operating under constrained conditions where ensuring high-quality care requires greater effort and vigilance. Minor delays, less personalized attention, or missed opportunities for early intervention might not be immediately visible but can accumulate over time and affect both patient satisfaction and clinical results.

2.3. Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout

Table 4: Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing in terms of Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1 Emotional exhaustion among staff	2.51	Often a Challenge
2 Inadequate emotional support and encouragement to the staff.	2.36	Slightly a Challenge
3 Difficulty retaining staff who may feel overworked, undervalued, and tempted to seek employment elsewhere.	2.48	Slightly a Challenge
4 Challenge in maintaining a harmonious and collaborative work environment	2.26	Slightly a Challenge
5 Challenge in providing growth and learning opportunities for the staff	2.22	Slightly a Challenge
Category Mean	2.37	Slightly a Challenge

Table 4 demonstrates the challenges encountered by the nurse managers in dealing with understaffing, specifically as regards addressing staff morale and burnout. Among the identified challenges, emotional weariness among personnel is prominent (M=2.51). This indicates that emotional tiredness is a substantial and persistent concern for nursing teams, possibly caused by excessive workloads, elevated patient-to-nurse ratios, and the emotional burden of caregiving under challenging circumstances. A significant issue pertains to the challenge of maintaining employees who may perceive themselves as overburdened, underpaid, or are contemplating other job opportunities (M=2.48). The result, although regarded as "slightly a challenge," suggests a threat to worker stability. The combination of insufficient emotional support (M=2.36) indicates a workplace atmosphere where employees may feel undervalued or unsupported, perhaps resulting in heightened turnover and compounding understaffing challenges.

Moreover, the difficulties in sustaining a harmonious and collaborative work environment (M=2.26) and in offering growth and learning opportunities for the staff (M=2.22) further reveal the complex effects of understaffing on collaboration and professional development. These factors are crucial for cultivating solid, motivated teams, and their lack can lead to a progressive deterioration in morale. Although these difficulties may seem little, they can mount over time and adversely impact employee engagement, performance, and organizational culture.

The category mean of 2.37 signifies that these issues are seen as "slightly a challenge," implying that, although not overwhelming, they occur frequently enough to require attention. Although the majority of issues are categorized as "slightly a challenge," the statistics indicate substantial consequences for employee well-being and retention. The persistently high ratings in multiple aspects of morale and burnout indicate that nurse managers feel pressured to provide emotional and professional support to their teams. Proactively addressing these concerns through supportive leadership, mental health services, and opportunities for recognition and development is essential for minimizing burnout and enhancing the long-term sustainability of the nursing profession.

2.4. Recruitment and Retention

Table 5: Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing in terms of Recruitment and Retention

	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	Struggling to attract qualified candidates due to competition from other healthcare facilities offering higher salaries, better benefits, or more flexible work environments	2.37	Slightly a Challenge
2	Competing with other hospitals and healthcare organizations offering better compensation packages and benefits	2.31	Slightly a Challenge
3	Relying on existing staff to work overtime can lead to fatigue, decreased job satisfaction, and higher turnover.	2.39	Slightly a Challenge
4	Managing the expectations of a diverse workforce which poses a challenge in recruitment and retention.	2.27	Slightly a Challenge
5	Limited opportunities for professional development, promotions, and further education	2.36	Slightly a Challenge
Category Mean		2.34	Slightly a Challenge

Table 5 shows the challenges encountered by the nurse managers in dealing with understaffing, specifically in connection with recruitment and retention. The main

challenge pertains to the dependence on current personnel to work overtime, potentially resulting in tiredness, discontent, and subsequent attrition (M=2.39). This signifies a reactive strategy to staffing shortages that may provide temporary relief but presents enduring dangers to employee welfare and retention. A notable challenge involves attracting qualified individuals (M=2.37), indicating increased difficulties in hiring new personnel. The competitive healthcare environment, especially with other institutions providing better compensation, enhanced benefits, or more flexibility in working conditions, is a significant challenge. Likewise, competing salary packages (M=2.31) underscore financial constraints within certain healthcare organizations, complicating the ability of nurse managers to attract and retain premier nursing talent.

Additionally, the difficulty of managing expectations within a diverse workforce (M=2.27) illustrates the complexity of addressing the numerous needs, values, and career aspirations of nursing personnel from various origins, generations, and specialties. The difficulty in offering professional development, advancement, and continuing education opportunities (M=2.36) could hinder retention by causing staff to feel stagnant or underappreciated.

The data about the challenges encountered by nurse managers in tackling understaffing, particularly with recruiting and retention, indicates that these issues are generally regarded as "slightly a challenge," with a category mean of 2.34. The persistent "slightly a challenge" ratings across all five factors indicate ongoing, low-level obstacles that may compound over time and adversely affect personnel stability. Although challenges in recruiting and retention are not deemed critical, their persistent occurrence across various dimensions indicates underlying structural problems that may result in ongoing personnel instability. Nurse managers are effectively managing through a competitive, resource-constrained landscape that compels them to optimize current personnel and contend with the challenge of recruiting new talent.

2.5. Managing Patient Expectations

Table 6: Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing in terms of Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout

	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	Quality of care may be compromised, making it difficult to meet patients' expectations for timely and personalized attention.	2.26	Slightly a Challenge
2	Less time to educate patients about their conditions, treatment plans, and discharge instructions	2.24	Slightly a Challenge
3	Cannot address patient complaints about delays, lack of attention, or perceived neglect on time	2.15	Slightly a Challenge

4	Inadequate time to provide the necessary attention to meet patients' needs.	2.21	Slightly a Challenge
5	Provision of frequent handoffs and staff changes, leading to a perceived lack of continuity.	2.27	Slightly a Challenge
Category Mean		2.23	Slightly a Challenge

Table 6 presents the challenges encountered by the nurse managers in dealing with understaffing, specifically in terms of managing patient expectations. The challenge that got the highest rating relates to frequent staff changes and handoffs (M=2.27), which may lead to patients perceiving a lack of continuity in their care. This issue, though rated as a slight challenge, indicates that patient trust and comfort could be compromised by the absence of familiar and consistent caregivers. Another major challenge is that the quality of care may be compromised, making it difficult for nurse managers and their teams to meet patient expectations for timely and personalized attention (M=2.26). This reflects how understaffing can subtly affect not only the efficiency but also the emotional and relational aspects of patient care.

A related challenge is the lack of time to properly educate patients about their conditions, treatments, or discharge plans (M=2.24). This limitation can lead to misunderstandings, non-compliance with instructions, or readmissions, ultimately affecting patient outcomes. Additionally, nurse managers face challenges in addressing patient complaints in a timely manner (M=2.15), which may cause patients to feel ignored or neglected. Although these are categorized as slight challenges, their cumulative effect can negatively shape patient perceptions of care quality and responsiveness. Lastly, the challenge of providing adequate attention to meet patient needs (M=2.21) points to a broader issue of strained nurse-patient interactions. When nurses are overwhelmed due to understaffing, even routine care can become rushed, diminishing the sense of compassion and attentiveness patients expect.

The data presented on the challenges encountered by nurse managers in managing understaffing, specifically in addressing patient expectations, reveal that these issues are perceived as "slightly a challenge," with a category mean of 2.23. While this suggests that the challenges are not yet overwhelming, they reflect consistent difficulties that can affect the overall patient experience. The findings may suggest that nurse managers are operating under strained conditions where they must balance limited staffing with rising patient demands and expectations. These challenges may not yet reach critical levels, but their continued presence signals underlying stress in care delivery systems.

2.6. Summary of the Challenges

Table 7: Summary of the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing

Category	Mean	Interpretation
A. Balancing Work Distribution	2.36	Slightly a Challenge
B. Maintaining Quality Care	2.14	Slightly a Challenge
C. Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout	2.37	Slightly a Challenge
D. Recruitment and Retention	2.34	Slightly a Challenge
E. Managing Patient Expectations	2.23	Slightly a Challenge
Overall Mean	2.29	Slightly a Challenge

The summary of challenges encountered by nurse managers in dealing with understaffing, based on the data presented, reveals that all identified categories are perceived as "slightly a challenge," with an overall mean of 2.29. This suggests that while these challenges are not currently seen as severe or overwhelming, they are present across various operational aspects and could potentially escalate if left unaddressed. The findings reflect a consistent pattern of low to moderate difficulty experienced by nurse managers as they manage staffing shortages and their impact on hospital functions.

Among the five categories, the highest mean score is observed in Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout (M=2.37), closely followed by Balancing Work Distribution (mean=2.36). This indicates that nurse managers are particularly challenged in ensuring fair workload allocation while also supporting the emotional well-being and motivation of their staff. Recruitment and Retention also scored relatively high (M=2.34), showing that nurse managers are encountering challenges in attracting and keeping qualified personnel. This may be due to competition from other healthcare institutions offering better compensation, more flexible schedules, or more appealing work environments.

On the other hand, Maintaining Quality Care and Managing Patient Expectations received slightly lower mean scores (M=2.14 and M=2.23, respectively), suggesting that while these areas are still impacted by understaffing, nurse managers may currently have systems or strategies in place to cope with these challenges to some degree. However, the consistent "slightly a challenge" rating still indicates a level of strain that could affect patient satisfaction and outcomes over time.

In general, although all categories fall under the "slightly a challenge" interpretation, the consistency of the findings across multiple areas of nurse management indicates a broader systemic issue. Nurse managers are under constant pressure to sustain operations despite limited staff, which places both personnel and patient care at risk. These slight challenges should not be overlooked, as they provide valuable insight into areas that require early intervention.

Part 3. Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Nurse Managers in Addressing Understaffing

Table 8: Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Nurse Managers in Addressing Understaffing

	Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1	I prioritize clear and open communication with staff to manage expectations, reduce stress, and promote teamwork during periods of understaffing	3.49	Always Employed
2	I delegate tasks to capable team members in distributing workload efficiently	3.45	Always Employed
3	I implement structured schedules and prioritize critical tasks to optimize available resources and maintain workflow	3.38	Always Employed
4	I collaborate with HR departments to expedite hiring processes or implement flexible staffing arrangements	2.88	Often Employed
5	I provide emotional support, recognize staff efforts, and foster a positive work environment.	3.26	Always Employed
6	I train nurses to handle multiple roles and responsibilities within the unit	3.37	Always Employed
7	I use technology, such as automated scheduling systems and communication tools, to streamline operations and improve efficiency in staffing management.	2.89	Often Employed
8	I advocate for additional resources and support from the hospital administration.	3.23	Often Employed
9	I adopt personal coping strategies, such as mindfulness, exercise, or seeking peer support, to manage stress and remain an effective leader.	3.34	Always Employed
10	I assess staffing strategies and solicit feedback from staff	3.40	Always Employed
Category Mean		3.27	Always Employed

Table 8 presents the coping mechanisms employed by the nurse managers in addressing understaffing. Among the ten strategies, the three highest-rated coping mechanisms are: prioritizing clear and open communication with staff (M=3.49), delegating tasks to capable team members (M=3.45), and assessing staffing strategies and soliciting feedback from staff (M=3.40). These top-rated practices reflect a strong emphasis on collaboration, trust, and responsiveness. Nurse Managers recognize that transparent communication promotes team unity and reduces stress, while efficient delegation ensures workloads are manageable. Regular evaluation and seeking

input from staff also demonstrate a commitment to continuous improvement and inclusive leadership, which are vital for maintaining a resilient workforce under pressure.

On the other hand, the three lowest-rated strategies, while still marked as "often employed," include collaborating with HR departments to expedite hiring or implement flexible staffing (M=2.88), using technology for scheduling and communication (M=2.89), and advocating for additional resources from hospital administration (M=3.23). These lower scores may reflect external constraints, such as limited technological infrastructure or challenges in securing administrative support. While nurse managers are willing to pursue these strategies, their ability to fully implement them may be restricted by factors beyond their direct control.

The data about coping strategies utilized by nurse managers to address understaffing indicate that these measures are consistently employed, obtaining a category mean of 3.27. This signifies a substantial level of proactive engagement among nurse managers in addressing staffing shortages. The majority of the strategies enumerated are employed consistently, emphasizing the management's dedication to sustaining operational stability and employee morale in the midst of challenges. The results indicate that nurse managers recognize the consequences of understaffing and are actively employing various strategies to mitigate its effects.

Part 4. Test on Significant Difference on the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers when Grouped According to Profile Variables

4.1 Age

Table 9: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Age

Age	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Balancing Work Distribution					
20-25 years old	2	4.00	8.862	5	0.115
26-30 years old	3	37.83			
31-35 years old	27	50.44			
36-40 years old	30	45.95			
41-45 years old	13	59.46			
46 years old and above	25	56.60			
Maintaining Quality Care					
20-25 years old	2	4.00	8.011	5	0.103
26-30 years old	3	7.00			
31-35 years old	27	49.85			
36-40 years old	30	46.52			
41-45 years old	13	57.04			
46 years old and above	25	56.32			

Age	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout					
20-25 years old	2	4.50	8.233	5	0.144
26-30 years old	3	34.00			
31-35 years old	27	49.87			
36-40 years old	30	47.90			
41-45 years old	13	54.15			
46 years old and above	25	58.06			
Age	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Recruitment and Retention					
20-25 years old	2	5.50	9.347	5	0.096
26-30 years old	3	25.33			
31-35 years old	27	49.24			
36-40 years old	30	48.70			
41-45 years old	13	56.31			
46 years old and above	25	57.62			
Age	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Managing Patient Expectations					
20-25 years old	2	5.50	8.686	5	0.118
26-30 years old	3	11.33			
31-35 years old	27	48.33			
36-40 years old	30	50.37			
41-45 years old	13	52.08			
46 years old and above	25	60.48			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was employed to assess whether statistically significant differences existed in the challenges encountered by nurse managers in managing understaffing when grouped according to their age. The analysis revealed that across all measured categories, there were no significant variations among age groups. This conclusion is supported by the fact that all p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance threshold, indicating that age does not play a decisive role in how nurse managers perceive or experience the challenges associated with understaffing.

These findings suggest that the challenges faced in managing understaffing are consistently experienced regardless of the nurse manager's age, highlighting that the issue is more likely systemic rather than age-specific. The acceptance of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level implies that age-related differences in coping with or encountering staffing challenges are statistically insignificant. This uniformity across age groups may point to shared institutional constraints or standard leadership responsibilities that affect nurse managers similarly, regardless of generational background.

4.2 Sex

Table 10: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Sex

Category	Sex	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
Balancing Work Distribution	Male	25	47.20	705.000	0.108
	Female	75	54.93		
Maintaining Quality Care	Male	25	44.80	745.000	0.102
	Female	75	55.73		
Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout	Male	25	41.66	716.500	0.077
	Female	75	53.45		
Recruitment and Retention	Male	25	41.40	710.000	0.069
	Female	75	53.53		
Managing Patient Expectations	Male	25	42.14	728.500	0.093
	Female	75	53.29		

The Mann-Whitney U Test was utilized to examine whether significant differences exist in the challenges encountered by nurse managers in addressing understaffing, based on their sex. The analysis compared the responses of male and female nurse managers across all identified challenge categories, such as balancing work distribution, maintaining quality care, staff morale, recruitment, and patient expectations. The results indicated that there were no significant differences between the two groups, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 threshold for significance.

This finding suggests that both male and female nurse managers perceive and experience the challenges related to understaffing in a relatively uniform manner. The acceptance of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level implies that sex does not significantly influence the way these challenges are encountered.

4.3 Years in Service

Table 11: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Years in Service

Years in Service	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Balancing Work Distribution					
5 years and below	5	40.40	1.518	2	0.468
6-10 years	32	47.14			
Above 10 years	63	53.01			
Maintaining Quality Care					
5 years and below	5	27.90	3.828	2	0.148
6-10 years	32	48.55			
Above 10 years	63	53.29			

Years in Service		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout						
5 years and below		5	40.10	2.067	2	0.356
6-10 years		32	46.16			
Above 10 years		63	53.53			
Years in Service		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Recruitment and Retention						
5 years and below		5	36.10	2.750	2	0.253
6-10 years		32	46.27			
Above 10 years		63	53.79			
Years in Service		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Managing Patient Expectations						
5 years and below		5	30.00	3.929	2	0.140
6-10 years		32	46.95			
Above 10 years		63	53.93			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was applied to explore whether nurse managers' length of service influenced their experiences of challenges related to understaffing. Specifically, the analysis aimed to determine if those with varying years of service, whether newly appointed or seasoned professionals, perceived these challenges differently across categories such as workload distribution, quality care, staff morale, recruitment, and patient expectations. The findings revealed that there were no significant differences among the groups, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance level.

This result implies that tenure or length of service does not significantly alter how nurse managers perceive or respond to the challenges posed by understaffing. Regardless of their experience level, nurse managers seem to face similar challenges, which suggests that these challenges are embedded within the broader healthcare system and are not necessarily mitigated or worsened by managerial seniority.

4.4 Highest Educational Attainment

Table 12: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Balancing Work Distribution						
Baccalaureate Degree		50	51.31	2.629	2	0.269
Master's Degree		49	50.62			
Doctorate Degree		1	4.00			

Highest Educational Attainment					
	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Maintaining Quality Care					
Baccalaureate Degree	50	50.36	2.687	2	0.261
Master's Degree	49	51.59			
Doctorate Degree	1	4.00			
Highest Educational Attainment					
	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout					
Baccalaureate Degree	50	50.59	2.580	2	0.275
Master's Degree	49	51.35			
Doctorate Degree	1	4.50			
Highest Educational Attainment					
	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Recruitment and Retention					
Baccalaureate Degree	50	49.38	2.753	2	0.253
Master's Degree	49	52.56			
Doctorate Degree	1	5.50			
Highest Educational Attainment					
	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Managing Patient Expectations					
Baccalaureate Degree	50	50.71	2.484	2	0.289
Master's Degree	49	51.20			
Doctorate Degree	1	5.50			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was employed to examine whether nurse managers' highest educational attainment had any bearing on their perceptions of challenges associated with understaffing. The goal was to identify whether those with varying academic backgrounds, such as bachelor's, master's, or doctoral degrees, perceive understaffing-related challenges differently across key categories. The statistical results showed no significant differences among the educational groups, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 threshold for significance.

This outcome suggests that educational level does not substantially influence how nurse managers experience the challenges of understaffing. Whether a nurse manager holds a basic nursing degree or an advanced graduate degree, the impact of staffing shortages appears to be uniformly felt across all roles. This uniformity indicates that practical, systemic pressures associated with understaffing may override the potential advantages conferred by higher educational qualifications.

4.5 Hospital Affiliation

Table 13: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Hospital Affiliation

Hospital Affiliation	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Balancing Work Distribution					
Hospital A	40	54.84	2.142	2	0.343
Hospital B	35	45.09			
Hospital C	25	51.14			
Maintaining Quality Care					
Hospital A	40	56.86	3.822	2	0.148
Hospital B	35	43.91			
Hospital C	25	49.54			
Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout					
Hospital A	40	55.79	2.236	2	0.327
Hospital B	35	47.06			
Hospital C	25	46.86			
Recruitment and Retention					
Hospital A	40	56.36	4.284	2	0.117
Hospital B	35	42.69			
Hospital C	25	52.06			
Managing Patient Expectations					
Hospital A	40	53.91	1.186	2	0.553
Hospital B	35	46.67			
Hospital C	25	50.40			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was conducted to assess whether the challenges faced by nurse managers in dealing with understaffing significantly differed based on their hospital affiliation. This statistical approach aimed to determine if variations in institutional settings might influence how nurse managers perceive and respond to staffing shortages. The analysis revealed that no statistically significant differences were observed across all categories, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance.

This finding implies a consistent experience of understaffing challenges among nurse managers, regardless of the hospital to which they are affiliated. It suggests that the pressures and operational burdens caused by understaffing are not isolated to specific institutions but rather reflect a broader, systemic issue common across healthcare facilities.

Part 5. Test on Significant Difference on the Coping Mechanisms Employed by Nurse Managers in Addressing Understaffing when Grouped According to Profile Variables

5.1 Age

Table 14: Differences in the Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Nurse Managers in Addressing Understaffing when grouped according to Age

Age	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Coping Mechanism					
20-25 years old	2	73.00	7.502	5	0.186
26-30 years old	3	57.00			
31-35 years old	27	49.39			
36-40 years old	30	41.52			
41-45 years old	13	48.85			
46 years old and above	25	60.76			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was employed to determine whether nurse managers' coping mechanisms in addressing understaffing varied significantly across different age groups. The statistical results showed no significant differences in coping strategies based on age ($H(5)=7.502$, $p=0.186$), as the p-value exceeded the standard significance level of 0.05. This finding suggests that age does not appear to influence how nurse managers respond to staffing shortages, and their approaches to coping remain relatively consistent regardless of generational differences.

The acceptance of the null hypothesis implies that coping behaviors among nurse managers are likely shaped more by professional experience, organizational culture, or situational demands rather than by their age group. This uniformity in coping responses may reflect standardized leadership training, shared institutional protocols, or a common set of values upheld in nursing leadership. From a managerial perspective, these findings emphasize the importance of reinforcing effective coping mechanisms across all age groups to ensure consistent and resilient leadership during staffing challenges.

5.2 Sex

Table 15: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Sex

Category	Sex	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
Coping Mechanism	Male	25	51.32	917.000	0.870
	Female	75	50.23		

A Mann-Whitney U Test was performed to evaluate statistically significant differences in the coping strategies utilized by nurse managers in response to understaffing, categorized by sex. The research indicated no substantial difference in coping behaviors between male and female nurse managers ($U = 917.000$, $p = 0.870$), as the p-value was significantly above the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that both male and female nurse supervisors employ comparable techniques and methods when faced with staffing deficiencies.

The acceptance of the null hypothesis indicates that sex does not significantly influence the management and response of nurse managers to understaffing situations. The uniformity in coping strategies between sexes may indicate the impact of common leadership training, organizational norms, or the inherent requirements of the nursing leadership position. This research emphasizes that effective coping in crisis management is more likely determined by professional competences and institutional practices rather than sex-related gaps, highlighting the necessity of inclusive and standardized support programs for all nurse leaders.

5.3 Years in Service

Table 16: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Years in Service

Years in Service Coping Mechanism	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
5 years and below	5	66.60	5.780	2	0.120
6-10 years	32	59.34			
Above 10 years	63	54.89			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was utilized to assess significant differences in the coping strategies implemented by nurse managers in response to understaffing, contingent upon their years of service. The findings indicated no substantial differences across the various service length categories ($H(2) = 5.780$, $p = 0.120$), since the p-value surpassed the 0.05 significance barrier. This indicates that the duration of a nurse manager's service does not significantly affect the coping techniques they employ in addressing staffing problems.

The acceptance of the null hypothesis indicates that, irrespective of a nurse manager's experience level, they are likely to employ comparable strategies in addressing understaffing. This uniformity across tenure levels may indicate standardized training, common institutional processes, or similar exposure to workplace management situations. These findings emphasize the necessity of providing all nurse managers, irrespective of experience, with realistic and flexible coping strategies, rather than supposing that tenure alone results in more successful responses.

5.4 Highest Educational Attainment

Table 17: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment Coping Mechanism	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Baccalaureate Degree	50	47.45	4.491	2	0.106
Master's Degree	49	54.62			
Doctorate Degree	1	1.00			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was employed to assess if nurse managers' coping strategies for managing understaffing significantly varied according to their highest level of educational achievement. The results indicated no significant differences across the educational groups ($H(2) = 4.491$, $p = 0.106$), since the p-value exceeded the 0.05 significance threshold. This outcome supports the acceptance of the null hypothesis, signifying that educational attainment—be it bachelor's, master's, or doctoral—does not exhibit a quantifiable influence on the coping mechanisms utilized by nurse managers.

This result indicates that, irrespective of academic qualifications, nurse managers are likely utilizing comparable institutional protocols, practical experiences, and collective leadership expectations when addressing understaffing challenges. This may suggest that practical managerial abilities and workplace adaptation are more significant in shaping coping behaviors than academic achievement alone. As a result, hospital administrations may gain by prioritizing practical leadership development programs instead of depending exclusively on academic qualifications to prepare nurse managers for workforce difficulties.

5.5 Hospital Affiliation

Table 18: Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing when grouped according to Hospital Affiliation

Hospital Affiliation Coping Mechanism	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Hospital A	40	42.48	5.369	2	0.068
Hospital B	35	57.34			
Hospital C	25	53.76			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was conducted to assess whether nurse managers' coping mechanisms for addressing understaffing varied significantly across different hospital affiliations. The analysis revealed no statistically significant differences ($H(2)=5.369$, $p=0.068$), as the computed p-value exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis is upheld, indicating that the coping strategies

employed by nurse managers do not significantly differ based on the specific hospital to which they belong.

This finding implies a general consistency in the approaches adopted by nurse managers across institutions, suggesting that shared policies, professional standards, or common organizational pressures may be shaping uniform responses to staffing shortages. Despite potential variations in hospital size, resources, or management styles, the results suggest that nurse managers across different affiliations are likely facing similar constraints and resorting to comparable methods to mitigate the impact of understaffing. This could highlight the need for system-wide interventions or unified training programs aimed at strengthening managerial coping strategies across all healthcare settings.

Part 6. Test on the Significant Relationship between the Challenges Encountered in Dealing with Understaffing and the Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Nurse Managers

Table 19: Relationship between the Challenges Encountered in Dealing with Understaffing and Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Nurse Managers

Challenges	Coping Mechanisms	
Balancing Work Distribution	r	-0.072
	p-value	0.479
Maintaining Quality Care	r	-0.161
	p-value	0.109
Addressing Staff Morale and Burnout	r	-0.1
	p-value	0.322
Recruitment and Retention	r	-0.091
	p-value	0.369
Managing Patient Expectations	r	-0.158
	p-value	0.115

A Spearman's Rho correlation analysis was conducted to explore whether there is a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by nurse managers in dealing with understaffing and the coping mechanisms they employ. The results showed that no significant correlation exists between any of the identified challenges and the coping mechanisms used by the nurse managers, as all p-values were greater than the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that the extent of challenges experienced by nurse managers does not necessarily predict how frequently or effectively they implement particular coping strategies. In other words, regardless of whether the challenges were more or less severe, the nurse managers tended to apply coping strategies in a similar fashion.

These findings suggest that coping mechanisms may be employed out of routine professional practice or institutional policy rather than as a direct response to the severity

of the challenges encountered. It may also indicate that nurse managers possess a stable set of adaptive behaviors that they rely on consistently, regardless of the intensity of the understaffing issues they face. This insight highlights the potential need for more tailored and responsive coping interventions that align more closely with the specific difficulties being experienced in understaffed environments.

DISCUSSION

I. Profile of the Nurse Managers

The demographic characteristics of the nurse managers suggest a mature and experienced workforce, with the majority falling into mid to late career stages. This trend indicates a substantial pool of clinical and managerial experience, essential for sustaining the stability and effectiveness of healthcare systems (Labrague et al., 2022). Studies suggest that younger professionals may be deterred from entering or staying in the nursing profession due to issues such as high workload, stress, and limited career progression (Lai et al., 2023). This demographic imbalance highlights the importance of succession planning and retention strategies aimed at younger nurses to ensure the sustainability of nursing leadership.

Sex distribution among the nurse managers continues to reflect the traditionally female-dominated nature of the nursing profession. However, the increasing representation of male nurse managers points to a gradual shift toward greater gender inclusivity in healthcare leadership (Wei et al., 2020). This evolving demographic may influence leadership styles, communication dynamics, and even the perception of the profession itself. Gender diversity in leadership roles has been associated with enhanced decision-making, team collaboration, and innovation (Jangland et al., 2022).

In terms of qualifications and experience, the data reveal a highly educated and long-serving group of nurse managers. The prevalence of advanced degrees among respondents underscores a commitment to professional growth and evidence-based practice (Newham & Hewison, 2021). Long-term service often correlates with greater clinical competence and leadership maturity, which are vital in managing complex health care demands (Roche, 2021). The relatively even distribution of nurse managers across the selected hospitals also allows for meaningful comparisons in management practices and institutional cultures. Together, these demographic insights provide an understanding of the strengths and challenges within the current nursing leadership, emphasizing the need to support both experienced professionals and the development of emerging nurse leaders.

II. Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers in Dealing with Understaffing

The challenges faced by nurse managers in addressing understaffing are varied, touching on both personnel management and patient care. Although none of the challenges are currently regarded as essential, their ongoing existence across

operational domains indicates the need for awareness and proactive measures. The findings emphasize a situation in which nurse managers must consistently handle minor stressors that, if neglected, may develop into serious problems (Newham & Hewison, 2021). These pressures indicate the continuous effort to reconcile efficiency, employee welfare, and quality of treatment, which are all interconnected elements of hospital administration.

Supporting staff morale and minimizing burnout are among the most important considerations. Nurse Managers consistently encounter the challenge of maintaining team motivation while addressing emotional tiredness resulting from staff shortages and increased workloads (Goktepe et al., 2020; Lai et al., 2023). Likewise, ensuring an equitable allocation of responsibilities presents challenges, as it directly influences team dynamics and employees' perceptions of fairness. These problems highlight the emotional and practical intricacies of managing a healthcare team under duress. They underscore the importance of robust interpersonal skills and emotional intelligence in nursing leadership positions (Wei et al., 2020).

Recruitment and retention constitute an essential domain, as nurse managers contend with staff instability. The competition for proficient nurses is fierce, as many institutions frequently provide more appealing job circumstances, complicating the efforts of certain hospitals to acquire and maintain qualified staff (Jangland et al., 2022). Restricted career advancement opportunities or rigid schedules can increase employee turnover. Nurse Managers consequently confront the combined challenge of remedying current staffing shortages while formulating measures to improve long-term retention and work satisfaction (Orvik et al., 2020).

In contrast, ensuring quality care and controlling patient expectations seem to be more regulated domains, likely attributable to existing protocols or crisis adjustments formulated after prior staffing shortages. Nonetheless, even in these domains, the fundamental pressures persist, and ongoing dependence on coping strategies without systemic support could eventually impact care standards. While patient satisfaction may currently remain consistent, unfulfilled expectations and prolonged wait times might harm trust if staff strain continues (Roche, 2021). These findings indicate that even minor issues warrant attention to avoid subsequent effects.

The uniformity of "slightly a challenge" ratings across all categories should not be seen as insignificant. Instead, they reveal a widespread underlying of strain that, if overlooked, could develop into more significant problems. Nurse Managers are shouldering the burden of a strained system, striving to sustain balance with constrained resources. This scenario necessitates prompt interventions, institutional support, and policy modifications to enhance the capabilities of nurse leaders and protect both staff welfare and patient outcomes (Newham & Hewison, 2021; Wei et al., 2020; Roche, 2021).

III. Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Nurse Managers in Addressing Understaffing

The most highly regarded coping mechanisms utilized by nurse managers to mitigate understaffing are clear communication, efficient delegation, and the active participation of staff in decision-making processes. Emphasizing open and honest communication among team members nurtures a culture of trust and collaboration, crucial for sustaining team cohesion during times of workforce strain (Senek et al., 2020; Labrague et al., 2018). Assigning duties to competent team members not only facilitates a more equitable distribution of workloads but also empowers employees, enhancing job satisfaction and reducing burnout. Nurse Managers who consistently evaluate staffing strategies and seek input demonstrate adaptive leadership, responding to frontline difficulties and promoting ongoing organizational enhancement (Ofei et al., 2020; Park & Yu, 2020).

On the other hand, many coping mechanisms, while acknowledged and employed, seem to be applied less frequently or successfully, potentially due to environmental constraints. Collaboration with human resource departments to expedite hiring processes or establish flexible employment arrangements frequently faces administrative or institutional barriers, hindering the pace or extent of execution (Senek et al., 2020). The implementation of technology for scheduling and communication, although advantageous for improving operations, may be hindered by inadequate technological infrastructure or a deficiency in training resources. Advocating for more resources from hospital management, while essential, can be difficult due to conflicting goals and budget constraints. These characteristics collectively emphasize how systemic and environmental conditions might affect the extent to which nurse managers can use specific coping mechanisms (Labrague et al., 2018; Ofei et al., 2020).

The persistent utilization of various coping strategies by nurse managers demonstrates a proactive and resilient method for addressing understaffing. The commitment to preserving operational stability and employee morale during workforce shortages reflects an awareness of the substantial effects that understaffing has on care quality and staff welfare (Park & Yu, 2020). Nurse Managers' utilization of many tactics, ranging from interpersonal communication to structural modifications, illustrates their comprehensive approach to leadership in crisis scenarios. Their initiatives seek to resolve urgent staffing issues while also fostering a sustainable work environment that enhances both employee and patient results.

These findings highlight the necessity of providing nurse managers with sufficient resources, efficient administrative procedures, and technological investments to augment their ability to execute complete coping techniques. Promoting inclusive leadership and facilitating open conversation across teams are essential approaches that empower nurse managers to adeptly address the challenges of understaffing. As healthcare systems encounter workforce challenges, strengthening leadership competencies will be essential for maintaining resilience and guaranteeing quality patient care (Senek et al., 2020; Labrague et al., 2018; Ofei et al., 2020; Park & Yu, 2020).

IV. Test on Significant Difference on the Challenges Encountered by the Nurse Managers when Grouped According to Profile Variables

The study's findings indicate that nurse managers, irrespective of demographic profile such as age, sex, tenure, educational qualifications, and hospital affiliation, face comparable challenges in managing understaffing. The absence of a notable difference suggests that understaffing is a widespread problem in healthcare environments, impacting leaders uniformly, irrespective of their background or institutional context. Newham and Hewison (2021) assert that structural staffing deficiencies, rather than personal attributes, frequently determine the scope and nature of managerial difficulties in healthcare. This indicates that the problem is rooted in organizational frameworks and resource constraints rather than being affected by individual or institutional variability.

Moreover, Goktepe et al. (2020) affirm that issues associated with understaffing, such as employee burnout, diminished patient care, and workflow inefficiencies, are frequently encountered by nurse managers in various environments. Their findings emphasize that even experienced or highly trained nurse supervisors are not exempt from the consequences of ongoing staffing shortages. Wei et al. (2020) also emphasize that irrespective of demographic features, nurse managers generally exhibit analogous coping mechanisms and consistently identify similar stressors related to understaffing, indicating a common professional experience. This supports the assertion that these concerns surpass individual or institutional disparities and may originate from overarching systemic issues within the healthcare delivery framework.

Finally, Orvik et al. (2020) contend that organizational ethics and leadership practices frequently influence the management of difficulties rather than the individuals overseeing them. This analysis clarifies the absence of notable disparities across demographic or professional categories in this study. It suggests that strategies to mitigate understaffing should prioritize institutional rules, ethical leadership support, and resource distribution instead of concentrating on particular cohorts of nurse managers. The findings together underscore the necessity for comprehensive, organization-wide strategies to mitigate the widespread and consistent burden of understaffing across various healthcare settings.

V. Test on Significant Difference on the Coping Mechanisms Employed by Nurse Managers in Addressing Understaffing when Grouped According to Profile Variables

The findings indicating no significant differences in coping strategies employed by nurse managers across variables such as age, sex, years in service, educational attainment, and hospital affiliation suggest a shared, collective response to the common challenge of understaffing. This aligns with the study of Lai et al. (2023), who found that nurse managers tend to develop similar adaptive behaviors when confronted with staffing challenges, regardless of their background. The uniformity in coping mechanisms can be attributed to standardized leadership expectations and organizational protocols that guide managerial responses during workforce shortages.

Furthermore, Wei et al. (2020) and Jangland et al. (2022) reinforce the idea that coping strategies such as task delegation, emotional support for staff, and structured scheduling are often institutionally driven rather than individually tailored. These researchers highlight that nurse managers operate within similar regulatory and ethical frameworks, which influence their actions more than personal characteristics. As such, even nurse leaders with differing levels of experience or education often rely on the same fundamental practices to maintain quality care, staff morale, and operational efficiency during periods of understaffing.

Additionally, Roche (2021) and Tan (2021) emphasize the importance of resilience and consistent leadership behaviors in nursing management. They argue that effective coping strategies are generally learned through organizational culture and training, rather than being influenced by demographic attributes. This may explain why no statistically significant differences were found in this study across various groups. Ultimately, these findings suggest that the development and reinforcement of coping mechanisms are more dependent on institutional support and leadership development programs than on individual backgrounds, reinforcing the value of organization-wide interventions in addressing systemic staffing issues.

VI. Test on Significant Relationship between the Challenges Encountered in Dealing with Understaffing and the Coping Mechanisms Employed by the Nurse Managers

The findings that no significant correlation (although negatively correlated) exists between the challenges faced with understaffing and the coping techniques utilized by nurse managers indicate that the application of coping mechanisms may not be directly proportionate to the perceived degree of the challenges. This may suggest that nurse supervisors often employ uniform coping mechanisms, irrespective of their assessment of the severity or manageability of the understaffing issue. Roche (2021) emphasizes the existence of organizational protocols and systematic leadership programs that compel nurse managers to implement uniform strategies in response to staffing shortages. These institutionalized techniques may reduce the variability in coping reactions, despite changes in the intensity of the challenges.

Arakelian and Rudolfsson (2021) support this viewpoint by highlighting that nurse managers frequently operate within intricate healthcare systems that encourage standardized leadership characteristics. Their research suggests that coping mechanisms such as delegation, emotional support, or job prioritization are frequently incorporated into managerial training and organizational culture. Therefore, leaders may be encouraged to implement these approaches as standard procedures, irrespective of the particular staffing difficulties they face. This systematic approach promotes consistency and continuity of care; nonetheless, it may illustrate the absence of a significant association between the degree of challenge and the coping techniques employed.

Furthermore, Newham and Hewison (2021) observe that nursing leadership is significantly influenced by external factors, including policy expectations, staffing frameworks, and organizational culture. These features can standardize nurse supervisors' responses to stressors such as understaffing, rendering coping strategies more reactive to systemic norms than to individual assessments of challenge intensity. The lack of significant association in the current findings may indicate the impact of general structural factors, requiring nurse managers to exhibit uniform responses across different levels of difficulty instead of modifying their coping strategies according to the severity of the challenge.

Conclusions

In light of the presented findings, the following conclusions have been derived:

The demographic profile of the nurse managers reflects a seasoned and competent leadership group, characterized predominantly by female professionals with more than ten years of service in the field and holding bachelor's degrees.

Along with that, the consistent yet moderate challenges encountered by nurse managers in managing understaffing signify a significant, systemic pressure inside healthcare organizations that necessitates immediate and planned intervention. Although the concerns seem manageable at present, their ongoing presence in critical operational domains such as morale, task allocation, recruitment, and patient care indicates an unstable situation that may collapse without prompt action.

Moreover, the strategies employed by nurse managers reveal a strong commitment to maintaining team effectiveness and operational stability amidst the persistent challenge of understaffing. The consistent use of communication, delegation, and inclusive evaluation strategies reflects adaptive leadership that values collaboration and staff empowerment. However, the limited implementation of system-dependent strategies such as working with HR, leveraging technology, and securing administrative support implies the need for broader institutional backing.

In addition, the absence of significant differences in the challenges encountered by nurse managers in dealing with understaffing across different profile variables suggests that these challenges are widespread and consistent regardless of their demographic characteristics. This underscores the systemic nature of understaffing issues within healthcare settings, affecting all nurse managers similarly.

The lack of significant variation in the coping mechanisms utilized by nurse managers, when categorized by profile characteristics, suggests that nurse managers, irrespective of their demographic or professional backgrounds, apply similar methods to address understaffing issues. The finding indicates a mutual understanding and collective reaction strategy among nurse leaders in handling workforce shortages.

Lastly, the lack of a significant relationship between the challenges encountered in dealing with understaffing and the coping mechanisms employed by nurse managers suggests that the strategies used may not be directly influenced by the severity or nature of the challenges faced. This indicates that nurse managers might be relying on a consistent set of coping approaches regardless of the specific difficulties they experience.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered to improve practice, support policy formulation, and shape future interventions:

1. Implement structured workload management strategies, such as acuity-based staffing systems, real-time workload tracking, and cross-training programs. These measures can help nurse managers distribute tasks more equitably, optimize available staff during periods of understaffing, and minimize burnout risks.

2. Establish safety-focused protocols and supportive staffing measures to mitigate risks associated with understaffing. Strategies such as implementing double-check systems, prioritizing critical tasks, and utilizing technology for patient monitoring can help reduce errors and prevent delayed treatments.

3. Implement programs and strategies to support staff well-being and reduce emotional exhaustion. This may include providing access to counseling services, promoting stress management workshops, offering adequate rest periods, and ensuring fair workload distribution.

4. Develop sustainable staffing solutions to minimize reliance on existing staff working excessive overtime. Strategies may include hiring additional personnel, implementing flexible scheduling, and monitoring workload distribution.

5. Implement structured handoff protocols and continuity-of-care strategies to minimize disruptions caused by frequent staff changes. Measures such as standardized shift reports, detailed patient care documentation, and team-based care assignments can help maintain consistent patient care, reduce errors, and improve overall staff and patient satisfaction.

6. Collaborate actively with the Human Resources department to streamline hiring processes and implement flexible staffing arrangements.

7. Maximize the use of technology, such as automated scheduling systems, real-time communication tools, and workforce management software, to streamline staffing operations and improve efficiency.

8. Advocate actively for additional resources and support from hospital administration. By communicating staffing needs, requesting necessary equipment, and securing administrative backing, nurse managers can enhance the capacity of their units, reduce staff workload, and ensure safe and efficient patient care.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research study on the challenges and coping mechanisms of nurse managers in understaffing at the selected hospitals was conducted with the utmost adherence to ethical standards and moral principles. Before initiating the study, the researcher secured

informed consent from all participants, providing comprehensive information about the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Participants were assured that their participation was entirely voluntary, and their rights and well-being were prioritized at all stages.

The researcher upheld the autonomy of participants by allowing them to withdraw from the study at any time without repercussions. Efforts will also be made to minimize any potential harm or discomfort during the data collection process.

Upon completion of the study, the findings will be shared with the locale of the study to foster transparency and support evidence-based improvements in patient care and organizational management. The results will be presented accurately and reliably, serving as a foundation for capacity-building initiatives aimed at enhancing the efficiency, safety, and overall quality of care provided by the hospitals.

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